

NON EXISTENCE OF EMPTY SPACE

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Abstract:

We studies consciousness from empty or vacuum spaces which are filled with a series of new energies from the sources of SU(6), SU(12), SU(24),..... ∞ creating non local & local information as consciousness continuing with random symmetry breaking of different unified groups of energy in the scalar field tending by exerted forces from energies to the situation for construction like bounded close-dynamic-conscious body system in large scale physical universe as well as in small scale quantum universe.

Introduction:

The first stages of journey called open universe, assumed to be as mother stage or Almighty trying to create an infinite number of close physical universe or bounded close-dynamic-body system after changing of phase by repeated trial. Unfolding mass universe through nascent period called flat physical universe of exotic matter fluid stage constructing under the information of mother stage, appearing with a machinery system for random creation of individually separated bounded close-dynamic-matter body system in large scale conscious physical universe or multiple universe or miniature of large numbers of different lives or organisms with holographic virtual consciousness living within the physical universe as like as parasite. An analogy will illustrate the changing situation of wider universe for construction of physical universe, as like a non magnetism iron bar will trying to change in a magnetic bar by the friction process, then creates a magnetic bar after re-arranging the Weber particles. Again if we can split the created magnetic bar into more & more small parts, we found each parts is an individual separate magnets in small size whose fundamental characters are same as the bar magnet and so on. In the first stage of universe the distributed wave of energies are non aligned because its high momentum, practically causing non forming resultant force but it tends to convergent for apparent equilibrium under mutual interaction causing random symmetry breaking, after phase change when it reaches to a crucial symmetry breaking called Super Unified Theory of the Group SU(11) at 10-dimensional space-time with direct involvement of information from mother consciousness making blue-prints for everything of the unfolding physical universe and ultimately gifting many more free individual bounded dynamic close body-system after (10-7)-dimensional vapor like stages of flat universe in large scale then 5th & 6th dimensions concerning the black-hole stage and finally appears thermodynamically closed adiabatic conscious bounded dynamic body-system as

physical universe with individual Galaxies etc. and then expanding the dynamic body-system with material development through mutual interchange of bosons of the new energy sources of SU(6) & SU(5) and with spontaneously symmetry breaking of SU(5) gifting effective material masses by the energy sources of SU(3), SU(2), U(1). Within the close physical universe, created different kind of electromagnetic forces as local information or local consciousness by interaction between energy waves or boson particles of the sources SU(6) directly and indirectly by non-local informational groups SU(12), SU(24),,etc. through their respective frameworks of SU(6) \times U(1); SU(12) \times U(1); SU(24) \times U(1);.....etc. We found then random creation of billion & billion bounded different close-dynamic-body-system as individual lives activated with computer like monitor system creating various windows of holographic virtual consciousness at brain-like places then interacted with mind & intelligence etc. for advancing of smooth working including next generation. We now comparing the different stages of the aforesaid informational universe with the birth of human like, physically separating from mother-body then slowly grown of individual personalities by interacting through virtual consciousness as incoming information by mutual interaction with mind, intelligence, creates emotions etc. Mind is a powerful tools controlled everything externally & internally within the bounded dynamic close-body-system willingly or unwillingly like as computer software installed initially with hard-disk then upgraded repeatedly for smooth running of all-round development but unfortunately observing automatically installed some infectious virus software or malware etc. as like in the case of internet system for disturbance of smooth running, we need then to protect the system by installation of anti-virus-like or physically applying then drugs or medicine etc. of lives for physical protection as direct impact.

Detail Explanation of New Model:

The extra-dimensions above four are assumed to be associated with consciousness i.e. we consider the individual consciousness is (partly) an expression of universal consciousness. Again the 4-dimensional Einstein's space-time obtained from spontaneous symmetry breaking of the Unified Gaussian Theory of the energy group SU(5) [\supset SU(3) \times SU(2)] \times U(1)]. Assuming, quark-like particles of the strong force SU(6) producing in the early stage of Super Unified Gaussian Group SU(11) creates informational local consciousness and with lepton-type particles from relatively weak force of SU(5) after spontaneously symmetry breaking creating conscious close-dynamic-body-system as human [we assumed that in the first stage of SU(11), SU(6) creates strong forces while SU(5) creates weak forces like as QCD of SU(3) creates strong force & SU(2) creates weak forces] introducing a new dimension of physics as well as biology beyond standard model. In the second stage of SU(11), matter atoms created material masses of different elements in the physical universe by quarks & leptons from the strong forces SU(3) of QCD, weak forces SU(2) and electrodynamics U(1), where U(1) created magnetic mono-poles following the past information of first stage of SU(11). Therefore, new energy sources of SU(6) are fundamentally responsible

for the creation of local consciousness in the framework of $SU(6) \times U(1)$, after creating a new kind of electromagnetic force, through which it is virtually present in the human or live brain as local consciousness, then creating holographic picture with neutrino-electrical pseudo-current [$SU(6)$ having 35 number of bosons out of which 30 number of bosons i.e. 15 pairs of bosons are charge-like & 5 number of bosons are neutral as neutrinos-like making a pseudo current throughout the close dynamic-body-system as in the case of $SU(2)$ created neutral current by the pair of charge particles with neutral particles W^{+-} & Z^0 in the framework of $SU(2) \times U(1)$]. Therefore, no consciousness directly created in any place of the human or live brain or anywhere of the individual close dynamic-body-system except its present virtually which actively working as incoming information for smooth running of dynamic system. You therefore, imagine the close physical universe is a Wi-Fi region of network-system through local consciousness for connecting each individual close dynamic-body-system. If you go outside the physical material universe i.e. wider universe of another phase you have escape from your mind, intelligence & local consciousness etc., you then coincide with non-local eternal consciousness. Although it is possible only when the close physical universe become disappear within the open universe.

There created different kind of biological matter elemental parts for expansion of dynamical body-system of lives under $SU(6)$. The energy particles of $SU(6)$ are always remained in wave form but maintaining the law of entanglement as wave-wave duality while particles of $SU(5)$ maintaining the law of entanglement of wave-particle duality. Thus, human consciousness are coming from outside the close-body carried with information and created holographic picture by a kind of electro-magnetic forces in the framework of $SU(6) \times U(1)$ by random interaction with mind through superposition of wave functions by resonating vibrations. It was properly activated as individual human consciousness after creating of mind by $SU(2)$ in the framework of $SU(2) \times U(1)$ within the close-dynamic body-system for future smooth working individually with appearing of intelligence, emotions etc. Therefore, mind etc. was closely related to the matter oriented body-system and changes by interacting with consciousness frequently due to the resonating vibrations with repeated superposition of wave functions. We therefore, understand a network disturbance may appear with incoming information at the time of appearing virtually consciousness within live or human brain. In the theory of $SU(11)$, it is possible to change any of 30(thirty) latent energy bosons of $SU(6)$ into any of the 30(thirty) matter energy bosons of $SU(5)$ or vice-versa by the exchange of the J-bosons of $SU(11)$. So, in the theory of $SU(11)$ created an amount of exotic matter fluids or nascent matter by the time of exchanging the J-bosons of $SU(11)$. Assuming that in the first stage of $SU(11)$, the six quark-like particles as u, d.....etc. of $SU(6)$, each having a packet of 5-different types of quark-likes which are then interacted with each other internally within the bunch or externally others quark-like, which are therefore playing an important role to the formation of different kind of matter particles or elements such are assumed to be found recently at LHC experiment in CERN after the discovery of new flavor particle. Therefore, $SU(6)$ behaves like a programmer creating a blue-print of the whole physical universe including galaxies & lives etc. We therefore conclude, a material physical universe

appearing with two stages of symmetry breaking of the unified group SU(11) & SU(5) mentioned above like as through vapor & liquid stages with different heat but same temperature as in the case of vapor phase contain much more latent heat comparing to the liquid. That means with living soul & physically bounded dynamic matter-body system together constructed a conscious live or human. We therefore require a clarification of earlier stage beyond standard model other than traditional quantum physics causing for the appearance of non local consciousness. As well as local consciousness carrying information to the creation of everything and playing an important role including administrative attitude for the manufacturing of everything to the close bounded dynamic-body-system maybe for inanimate or animate with different organisms connecting by different material parts of lives or human and inspiring for the appearance of unfolding individuality. Local consciousness then developed the personalities through interaction of minds, intelligence etc. for better lifestyle. Once upon a day, an Artificial Intelligence dependant robot will be as human when its mind can interacts with universal consciousness virtually or directly.

Conclusion:

Finally, we conclude the so called vacuum space was not originally empty rather it is Almighty, the space was filled with new energies creates super consciousness with non local information unfolded the local informational consciousness with everything of inanimate & animate of the physical universe including created human & live based on local consciousness.

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